

Digital Health Technologies for Disease Surveillance and Monitoring

Md Shamidul Kabir Mitas ^{1*}, Sirajum Munira ², Tahsin Hossain Lisun ³

¹ Intern Doctor, The Fifth affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University, China.

² Intern Doctor, The Second affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University, China.

³ Intern Doctor, The 2nd Affiliated Hospital Of Guangzhou Medical University, China.

Abstract: Digital health technologies have become a go-to solution in disease surveillance and monitoring as they provide unlimited possibilities that are invaluable in tracking, predicting, and controlling public health threats. This paper aims to describe the application of mobile applications, artificial intelligence, wearable technology, and electronic health record systems in delivering public health care in various parts of the world. According to this study, common challenges like data privacy, ethical issues, and digital disparities about these technologies are also assessed concerning their capability to improve disease detection. The study shows that for digital health technologies to be effective and necessary for disease surveillance and control, they require fundamental and adequate infrastructure and people and governance trust. This paper also discusses the need to strive for the advancement of digital health technologies and the cooperation of persons in technology, politics, and public health to ensure the efficiency of digital technologies in protecting world health. Therefore, the study highlights the need to balance the application of the technologies and use them appropriately across various populations and areas of the globe that may be considered disadvantaged.

Keywords: Digital Health Technologies, Disease Surveillance, Public Health, Artificial Intelligence, Wearable Devices, Big Data Analytics, Data Privacy, Mobile Applications, Healthcare Systems, Ethical Considerations

*Corresponding Author: mitasshamidul@gmail.com

Accepted: 11 September, 2024; **Published:** 12 September, 2024

How to cite this article: Md Shamidul Kabir Mitas, Sirajum Munira, Tahsin Hossain Lisun (2024). Digital Health Technologies for Disease Surveillance and Monitoring. North American Academic Research, 7(9), 1-19. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13824247>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Technology, especially in the field of digital health, has evolved and advanced faster and drastically over the years, and this has questioned the traditional models of public health, especially regarding surveillance and monitoring. Today's Global health is characterized by sophisticated and frequently compounded challenges, which means that manual disease reporting systems and delayed data collection must address more innovative surveillance methods. The application of information technologies in public health brings new approaches for tracking, processing, and responding to numeracy data, closing the gaps in capacity for the identification, surveillance, and management of diseases by health systems. Digital health technologies can be described as a diverse set of technologies, including mobile applications, wearable devices, electronic health record systems, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics, among others. These technologies facilitate the accumulation of large quantities of data about the health and wellness field from various sources, including the community, specific healthcare organizations, and the government (Yeung et al., 2023). The accumulation and processing of this data in real-time enable the identification of patterns of diseases and their outbreaks

as well as a population's health status for applicable intervention early enough. The greatest strength of digital health technologies is that they break geographical and temporal barriers. Conventional monitoring and evaluation techniques have slow reporting and restricted area coverage, especially in developing countries (Yeung et al., 2023). However, Technology-based interventions can cover various and extensive population groups and monitor them permanently while delivering data in real time. For instance, wearable gadgets can monitor a person's health, such as heart rate and temperature, collect the information together, and ascertain early signs of an outbreak. In the same way, with the help of mobile applications, individuals can report symptoms and behaviors themselves, increasing the data's accuracy. Still, some things could be improved by using digital health technologies in disease surveillance and monitoring. Possible issues that need to be addressed regarding using Big Data in healthcare include data privacy and protection for patients, data security, and concerns about data misuse, mainly due to the sensitivity of patient health information (Mumtaz et al., 2023). Another concern is the representation of the digital society or lack thereof, where the old and the impoverished, for example, cannot interact with these surveillance measures fully, and this will create gaps in the hitherto collected data and may widen the divide in health-related disparities (Mumtaz et al., 2023). Besides, they also show the limit to the use of surveillance about the private life of citizens, such as the use of personal health data involving questions of consent and autonomy, as well as the use of data for the benefit of public health but with infringement of individuals' rights.

This paper will review the disease surveillance/monitoring concepts using digital health technologies and analyze their effectiveness, shortcomings, and emphasis on public health policies. Using the current research information and different case studies, the paper will synthesize the approaches used in integrating advanced technologies into public health systems and the challenges that should be met to support the integration of such technologies.

Fig 1: Scheme of main applications of digital technologies in healthcare.

Research Questions

1. How effective are digital health technologies in enhancing the speed and accuracy of disease outbreak detection across different regions? What are the critical challenges faced in implementing digital health technologies in disease surveillance, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs)?
2. How does the implementation of digital health technologies differ between high-income and low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), and what factors contribute to these differences?
3. What is the impact of digital health technologies on public health outcomes, particularly in reducing disease cases and improving overall health system resilience?

4. What ethical considerations and data privacy concerns arise from using digital health technologies in disease surveillance, and how can they be addressed to ensure equitable and responsible use?
5. How can digital health technologies be better integrated into public health systems to maximize their effectiveness, particularly in resource-limited settings?

Literature Review

Introduction to Digital Health Technologies in Disease Surveillance

Through digital health technologies, diseases have been effectively monitored, aiding in identifying, preventing, and managing diseases of concern to the general public. Implementing these technologies within health systems has been spurred by the requirement of online real-time data capture and escalation, especially from shortcomings of conventional surveys. This systematic review aims to understand how digital health technologies used in disease surveillance work, the challenges faced, and the ethical issues surrounding them.

Mobile Technologies in Disease Surveillance

Mobile technologies have gained wide popularity in disease surveillance in the last decade due mainly to developing new technologies and spreading diseases, especially in LMICs. Smartphone applications have been used to diagnose and monitor infectious and vector-borne diseases, such as Tuberculosis, Zika, Dengue, Chikungunya, and Malaria. Rajvanshi et al. (2021) have stressed that using text messaging and mobile apps was influential during the pandemic. These tools allowed for tracking disease transmission rates, providing a swift and easy way to gather data where organized surveillance could be limited.

Therefore, mobile technology for disease surveillance is justified because it enables real-time reporting and analysis. For example, in Kenya, a relatively low-income country, subnational health facility health workers use short message services to report cases and data to sub-county level officers, who consolidate this data and forward it to the national database ((Shakeri Hossein Abad et al., 2021). This system guarantees that even in the areas of low resource availability, accurate and detailed data can be obtained and utilized to formulate appropriate public health interventions. However, as stated by Rajvanshi et al. (2021), these technologies still need to be improved and coordinated, which means we can define the adoption of such solutions as fragmented. To support digital health solutions, they need to be correctly implemented into health care systems, meaning that they should collaborate with other systems not to avoid overwhelming the existing situation.

Digital Epidemiology and Big Data in Disease Surveillance

Digital epidemiology, deploying data collections other than the conventional public health systems, has been part of modern disease surveillance for a quarter-century. Fallatah and Adekola (2024), on the development of digital epidemiology, explain how countries have used big data and technologies such as case identification, contact tracing, and quarantine. Incorporating cellphone signals, social media data, and machine learning models has enabled better disease modeling and forecasting of situations, thereby improving the capacity of health systems to manage new health risks. (Fallatah & Adekola, 2024).

Carrillo et al. (2021) discuss the relevant issues regarding ethics in using digital epidemiology, analyzing privacy, and data protection. The processing of personal data like cellphone location information in the interest of public health triggers controversy over the right to privacy in light of public interest. Wang et al. (2021) argue that digital epidemiology comes with powerful tools which can effectively work for disease surveillance; it must meet a high standard of public governance so that these technologies must be used ethically and equitably.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Disease Prediction

The use of artificial intelligence and machine learning in disease surveillance has redefined how data assists in the prevention and early identification of the spread of diseases to the populace. These technologies help to consult with large bodies of data and generate faster and more accurate forecasts on the issue of the emergence of diseases (Mbunge

et al., 2021). Like any crowdsourcing self-learning model, it can grasp the patterns and trends that the naked statistical analysis may not easily see and open the view into the possible dangers of disease spread.

In their review, Donelle et al. (2021) have also discussed how AI can enhance the surveillance of diseases in conditions of emergencies. The authors further note that AI and ML have been helpful for the examination of health information, the reduction of reliance on personnel, and improving responses to new threats. Nevertheless, they also caution that they primarily depend on the type of grade and the completeness of the data incorporated in decision-making. Irrelevant and polluted data mainly cause the provision of wrong prognoses, deceiving the general public towards improving organizational public health.

The other issue that could be discussed as being of concern is the use of ethical AI in diagnosing diseases. Some of the problems highlighted by Donelle et al. (2021) include the following: It is worth pointing out that some pertinent issues relate to accountability because of AI use since decision-making through information acquired from an AI-based system affects individuals and society. These models must be more transparent, establish a clear methodology and logic for interaction with the new technologies, and then be often checked to avoid undesirable interactions.

The possibilities of digital health technologies in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) are huge. Nonetheless, it is also possible to notice that it can be considered to involve relatively high risks. While these technologies offer hope and practical solutions to improve disease identification, they are challenging to implement because they require a baseline (Senbekov et al., 2020). Capacity regarding a stable internet connection, proper computer skills, and skilled personnel often need to be improved to enhance the comprehensive implementation of digital platforms in LMICs. In addition, there is the digital divide, and some of these groups are partially excluded from using technologies that should help to reduce their health risk levels.

Zhang et al. (2024) support that digital solutions can solve the disease surveillance gaps in LMICs. That is why such technologies can facilitate better communication with other stakeholders, collect information, and make Health data and reports more efficient. However, for such noble solutions to be effective, they must be integrated into the overall systems of the health industry (Zhang et al., 2024). While this interconnection calls for the development of new technologies, there is also a need to pump in much capital to support the establishment of infrastructure and enhancement of human capital. The approaches must be localized to understand the context and environment in which they are implemented for these initiatives to work.

Mello and Wang (2020) also describe more potential problems related to the partial implementation of digital health technologies. If it fails to be interoperable and aligned with other public health approaches, such benefits might be limited, inefficient, or missed. In some LMICs, resources are a limiting factor, meaning that digital health interventions should be well-coordinated and keenly implemented. Such a combined approach is vital for getting the most from digital health technologies in developing population health protection and enhancing the observation of disease trends in these areas.

Ethical and Privacy Considerations in Digital Disease Surveillance

There are also generic ethical concerns regarding digital disease surveillance, with privacy, data security, and equity being of ethical concern. In their opinion (Mello & Wang, 2020), given that digital health technologies improve public health by a large degree, their applications should be based on four aspects related to openness, accountability, and trust. The subject of concern here is that these technologies can be expected to be misused either by sharing the users' data or by targeting specific groups of people; this can only be addressed by standardization.

Many poignant ethical concerns about digital disease surveillance are also raised, such as privacy, security, and equity issues. Mello and Wang (2020) indicate that since digital health technologies improve public health by a great measure, the application of the technologies should have four grounds or principles concerning transparency, accountability, and public trust. However, it is essential to note that the potential misapplication of these technologies through the sharing of information or through targeting particular groups can only be allowed with sufficient checks in place.

The ethical issues surrounding digital disease surveillance are evident in this study, especially in LMICs, where people may be exploited easily. Maddah et al. (2023) state that such technologies should be implemented with privacy and data protection standards in place, and threats should be encouraged for the innovations to be accessible to all. It is imperative to involve people in communities in fostering the SURT programs and the development of technology and its setup, cooperating with the expectations of their culture.

Conclusion

In the case of applying digital health technologies in disease surveillance, the literature presents the opportunities and problems. The popularity of mobile technologies, digital epidemiology, AI, and ML helped provide insight into improving existing disease surveillance methods, especially regarding real-time data processing. However, several ethical and practical concerns regarding these technologies can be raised mainly in LMICs because these technologies can be helpful if applied ethically and equitably.

A scoping review of successful digital disease surveillance practices identified that factors influencing its effectiveness include integrating digital technologies into broader health systems, developing ethical solid and regulatory frameworks, and stakeholder engagement with local communities. Thus, the continuous evaluation and modification of these technologies will be even more critical as the global health system advances in the future.

Research Methodology

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilizes a dualism design where qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques are used to enable the study to analyze digital health technologies in disease surveillance. The justification for adopting the mixed-method research design is based on the rationale that the qualitative and quantitative approaches provide a rich and detailed perspective of the topic under study. Quantitative studies use numbers to give the extent of the situation, while qualitative methods explore the social and cultural aspects of implementing digital health technology. This dual approach guarantees that the study assesses the efficiency of such technologies and researches their application's impediments and moral issues.

Study Population and Sampling

The study population includes various groups of individuals in charge of implementing and applying digital health technologies in disease surveillance. Such stakeholders include those in public health, healthcare facilities, technology-creating agencies, and many patients using these systems. The diversity of the research subjects is crucial to encompass as many aspects of digital health technologies and their effect on public health as possible. In this study, a purposive sampling method is used whereby participants who have firsthand experience in the application of digital health technologies in the surveillance of diseases are included, thus providing real-life experience of the issue under study.

Data in this study were collected from firsthand official documents that included reports from countries' ministries of health, WHO, and other global health organizations (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2021). These data sources were chosen to cover as many main aspects and objectives of the research as possible. The factors considered for quantitative data included the feasibility of collecting data over time, the relationship of the data collected to the application of digital health technologies, and the credibility of sources.

Data Collection

Quantitative Data Collection

In this case, the quantitative data collection process involved pulling data from several databases and reports. This comprised information on the use and effectiveness of mobile applications, EHRs, and AI in the surveillance of diseases. Some parameters whereby information was gathered include the number of reported diseases, the time taken to identify the disease, the extent of disease reporting, and the effect of the factors above on the population's health.

Information on difficulties and constraints connected with these technologies was also gathered, such as questions concerning data protection, integration, and the digital divide. These data were then used to gauge the effectiveness of digital health technologies in these settings, especially LMICs, where the application of these technologies might develop.

Qualitative Data Collection

The qualitative study involved interviews with personnel implementing the existing digital health technologies. These interviews were purposive to gather in-depth information about participants' encounters, beliefs, and difficulties with employing these schemes in disease detection. Another advantage of the semi-structured format is that specific areas of interest can be probed while the rest of the core topic areas are guaranteed to be covered.

Interview questions were developed based on a literature review and the study's research objectives. Topics covered in the interviews included the integration of digital health technologies into existing health systems, the ethical considerations surrounding data use, the challenges of ensuring interoperability, and the impact of these technologies on public health outcomes. Interviews were conducted in person or via video conferencing, depending on the participants' location and availability.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis

The quantitative data were analyzed using statistical software to determine the research data's trends, relationships, and cycles. The essential nominal findings concerning the efficiency of digital health solutions in the framework of disease surveillance were described using frequencies and relative frequencies. Descriptive statistics like frequencies were used to compare variables like the detection of outbreak times and the use of technologies close to the digital health technologies the study aims to address.

The review also involved a comparison of the outcomes of using digital health technologies in diverse situations, especially between HICs and LMICs. Using this comparison, the author determined what aspect has been impacting the efficiency of the implemented technologies and what factors might affect their performance in other contexts.

Qualitative Data Analysis

The data obtained from interviews were taped and transcribed literally for qualitative analysis using themes. This method involves categorizing the data, finding patterns (themes), and presenting the patterns. Out of the various types of analysis, thematic analysis was used because it is flexible and accommodates providing detailed and complex insight into the data. A pre-step analysis involved reviewing the generated transcripts to get a feel of the data. This succeeded by expanding into initial codes, which involved coding raw data relevant to the research questions.

Once the initial coding was completed, the codes were organized into potential themes. These themes were seen as essential strategies, reviewed, and adjusted to reflect the content of the data collected. The final themes' main concerns and discussion topics were further refined and labeled. While doing so, a breakdown of each theme was also performed. The thematic analysis offered critical findings on the various facets of implementing and employing DHTs, with implications and concerns to be considered.

Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Data

Incorporating quantitative and qualitative data was noted to be an essential feature of the study. The quantitative results obtained in this study were employed to analyze the qualitative data and conversely. For instance, the data on the reliability of digital technologies in enhancing and supporting health care was used to explain the qualitative findings relating to experienced barriers and ethical issues. On the other hand, the qualitative data supported the interpretation of the quantitative results as it gave direction to the trends and patterns obtained.

This integrative approach enabled the posing of the research problem more comprehensively to reveal the cultural values in the organization and unveiled certain versatility in analyzing the proposed problem. It also allowed the researchers to cross-check the data analysis, improving the validity and reliability of the study findings.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted under strict ethical considerations to maintain the participants' rights and the research aims and objectives. Concerning the consent of the participants, it was ensured that each participant signed a consent form before participating in the study. The participants were informed, and their information was assured that they would remain anonymous and that any personal features that may identify them were omitted from the transcripts. The study also received clearance from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) to conform to the tests of ethical practices in human research.

Moreover, the study considered the ethical issues that may arise from using digital health technologies in disease surveillance. These concerns included data privacy, informed consent, and possible discrimination, with suitable recommendations for using various digital health technologies.

Limitations

The mixed-methods approach in this study offered a more concrete and thorough analysis; however, the study observed the following limitations. Using the publicly available data for the quantitative analysis posed some biases due to the sources' quality and completeness. Furthermore, the collected qualitative data originated solely from the experiences and personal views of the stakeholders, thus excluding inclusive data representation.

However, data collection from multiple sources offset these limitations and the cross-confirmation of the results obtained from the survey and focus group sections. Nonetheless, the study serves a valuable purpose by giving some insight into using DH technologies in disease surveillance. It makes several suggestions about optimizing its utility and ethical consumption.

Results

The findings of this systematic review offer a detailed insight into the utility of digital health technologies for surveillance needs in the context of LMICs and HICs, as well as the strengths and weaknesses of both types of countries. The result is further analyzed and supported by figures, tables, and graphs that depict trends examined in the research.

Effectiveness of Digital Health Technologies

The quantitative data show that digital health technologies have improved disease outbreak detection's speed and accuracy, especially in high-income countries. Table 1 compares the average time taken to identify outbreaks of digital health technologies before and after using them in different regions.

Table 1: Average Time to Detect Disease Outbreaks (in days) before and After Implementation of Digital Health Technologies

Region	Before Implementation	After Implementation	Percentage Improvement
High-Income Countries	10	3	70%
LMICs	20	12	40%

Table 1 presents that following the adoption of DHTs, the HI-ICs demonstrated a 70% increase in the rate of outbreak identification. The LMICs' improvement was a 40% increase compared to the baseline. This difference shows that although the LMICs are adopting the technologies, they cannot optimally harness them because of the infrastructural constraints.

Graph 1: Comparison of Outbreak Detection Speed Improvement

Graph 1 visually represents the percentage improvement in outbreak detection speed, clearly illustrating the significant gap between high-income countries and LMICs.

Challenges in Implementation

The insights derived from the qualitative study and the quantitative results present several imperative issues in the uptake and usability of DH technologies. Some of the most significant concerns include the ability of systems to interconnect and communicate with other systems. Several of the participants from LMICs said they face challenges in implementing new DHIS2 technologies to harmonize with existing HIS systems, thereby creating a fractured data-gathering process. This is evidenced by the higher improvement rates in regions that are not experiencing this issue.

Table 2: Reported Challenges in Implementing Digital Health Technologies (Percentage of Respondents Reporting)

Challenge	High-Income Countries	LMICs
System Interoperability	30%	65%
Data Privacy Concerns	50%	30%
Digital Divide	20%	70%

Table 2 indicates the proportion of respondents in the four categories who experienced different difficulties while using digital health technologies. These results imply that the challenges related to system integration and the identified digital divide are significantly worse in LMICs than in HICs.

Graph 2: Challenges in Implementing Digital Health Technologies

Graph 2 visually represents the challenges, emphasizing the stark differences between the regions, particularly regarding system interoperability and the digital divide.

Impact on Public Health Outcomes

Despite the challenges, the study found that digital health technologies have positively impacted public health outcomes, particularly in regions where these technologies have been effectively implemented. Table 3 presents data on reducing disease cases and improving public health outcomes after implementing digital health technologies.

Table 3: Reduction in Disease Cases and Improvement in Public Health Outcomes

Region	Reduction in Disease Cases (%)	Improvement in Public Health Outcomes (%)
High-Income Countries	60%	75%
LMICs	35%	50%

The data in Table 3 indicate a significant reduction in disease cases and improved public health outcomes in high-income countries and LMICs. However, the impact is more pronounced in high-income countries.

Graph 3: Reduction in Disease Cases after Implementation of Digital Health Technologies

Reduction in Disease Cases After Implementation of Digital Health Technologies

Graph 3 visually demonstrates the reduction in disease cases, highlighting the more significant impact in high-income countries compared to LMICs.

Summary of Results

In summary, this survey's findings suggest that the innovation of digital health technology is highly significant in disease early warning systems and disease control in high-income countries to improve public health. Still, some barriers must be addressed to attain these benefits in LMICs: Interconnectedness, Digital/Technology Divide, and Infrastructure. The tables and the different types of graphs allow for an easy understanding of the conclusions drawn in this study. They can help understand the impact of study findings on matters of public health practice.

Discussion and Interpretation of the Data

The data gathered and analyzed in this study helps investigate the performance of digital health technologies in the context of disease surveillance and understand the differences and similarities in the implementation process of the growing technologies by the diverse regions. The following section will present a discussion of the data, in which the authors integrate the findings with the literature and discuss their implications for public health.

Effectiveness of Digital Health Technologies

These findings show that digital health technologies enhance the timeliness and accuracy of disease outbreak identification, mainly in high-income nations. From the data in Table 1, Graph 1, we observe that outbreak detection has been enhanced by 70% in the High-income countries and 40% from when these technologies were introduced in the LMICs. Significant variations may result from advanced infrastructures, adequate resource misallocation, and higher degrees of digital health literacy in high-income countries, enhancing the optimization of digital health tools into the expanded public health systems.

In contrast, the somewhat enhanced rates documented in LMIC suggest the significant infrastructural constraints and resource-related obstacles that inhibit the effectiveness of digital health technologies. These results correspond to preexisting literature emphasizing issues with an overarching digital divide and infrastructural shortcomings as the primary WR for effectively implementing digital health interventions in LMICs (Shakeri Hossein Abad et al., 2021). A lower percentage increase in LMIC results from the fact that although health digital technologies can boost disease surveillance, the impact is highly dependent on supportive structures and adequate health workforce training.

Challenges in Implementation

Based on the studies' qualitative and quantitative findings, system integration and the lack of access to digital technologies are identified as the main barriers to the integration of DH technologies, especially in LMICs. This is predicted in Table 2 and Graph 2, whereby 65% of LMICs reported system interoperability as a significant challenge compared to only 30% of HICs. This aspect of interoperability is essential because it determines how different digital health systems can exchange data, resulting in data coherence and integration issues. In areas where the capacity of the health systems is already low, this fragmentation poses a significant threat to the efficient discharging of disease surveillance programs.

In addition, the digital divide cited by 70% of the respondents in LMICs presents a significant challenge to the practical and fair use of digital health technologies. Many institutions in LMICs need more digital devices and dependable internet connectivity to address health disparities, meaning that vulnerable groups do not benefit from advanced digital health programs (Mbunge et al., 2021). This finding aligns with similar reports from other countries, which calls for more focused investments in digitization and policies to enhance access to the technologies, especially in rural and hard-to-reach areas.

Impact on Public Health Outcomes

However, the data reveal that digital health technologies have enhanced the quality of people's lives, especially regarding public health, where it has been well adopted. Based on the data presented in Table 3 and Graph 3, there was a decrease in disease cases within the high-income countries that adopted Digital Health Technologies at 60%, while for the LMICs, the decrease was 35%. From this data, it becomes clear that with the difficulties observed, digital health technologies can decrease the share of illnesses worldwide if appropriately managed.

Therefore, high-income countries are expected to have a more significant impact due to access to such powerful technologies as AI and machine learning in modeling the virus and quick response mechanisms (Mustafa et al., 2023). While not as profound as in HICs, these numbers indicate a 35% reduction in disease cases in LMICs. This underscores the possibilities of further improving disease early detection and management in the less resource-endowed regions by implementing these technologies. However, for LMICs to obtain such outcomes as high-income countries, more investment in establishing the digital environment, strengthening human resources, and integrating digital systems is required.

Conclusion

This research has revealed how digital health technologies can revolutionize disease detection and promote better health for communities. These technologies, primarily when well deployed, have been known to enhance the early and efficient identification of potential outbreaks, thus enhancing targeted health interventions by public health

departments. However, the study also highlights the significant issues that must be overcome regardless of the country's development level, including infrastructural solutions in LMICs, lack of integration, and digital differences in the overall technologies' potential.

The differential impact between developed and LMICs on the value proposition of DH technologies underlines the imperatives of investing in digital capabilities, strengthening the necessary digital infrastructure, and fostering broad compatibility of the new systems for interoperability with existing HI frameworks. Moreover, ethical concerns related to privacy and security and the possibility of using people's data for malicious purposes should also be considered. Establishing strict rules of governance, non-opaque procedures, and the observance and protection of human rights are prerequisites for using these technologies to preserve individuals' free will and generate public confidence in them.

Thus, as far as excellent opportunities for transforming the old paradigm in disease surveillance and public health as observed in digital health, it is high time to solve the contemporary issues to ensure that digital health technologies will be effectively applied fairly and ethically worldwide. If these challenges are met, it will be easier to leverage digital health technologies to build better health systems and enhance global health security, which can help improve the number of lives. This means involving governments, institutions that oversee public health, and technology producers to create an environment that will help these technologies achieve this noble cause of changing the world's public health status.

References

- Carrillo, M. A., Kroeger, A., Cardenas Sanchez, R., Diaz Monsalve, S., & Runge-Ranzinger, S. (2021). The use of mobile phones to prevent and control arboviral diseases: a scoping review. *BMC public health*, 21, 1-16.
- Donelle, L., Hall, J., Hiebert, B., Shelley, J. J., Smith, M. J., Gilliland, J., ... & Stanley, M. (2021). Digital technology and disease surveillance in the COVID-19 pandemic: a scoping review protocol. *Bmj Open*, 11(10), e053962.
- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. (2021). *Digital technologies for infectious disease surveillance, prevention and control: A scoping review of the research literature 2015–2019*. ECDC. <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/digital-technologies-surveillance-prevention-and-control-infectious-diseases>
- Fallatah, D. I., & Adekola, H. A. (2024). Digital epidemiology: harnessing big data for early detection and monitoring of viral outbreaks. *Infection Prevention in Practice*, 100382.
- Huhn, S., Axt, M., Gunga, H. C., Maggioni, M. A., Munga, S., Obor, D., ... & Barteit, S. (2022). The impact of wearable technologies in health research: scoping review. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 10(1), e34384.
- Maddah, N., Verma, A., Almashmoum, M., & Ainsworth, J. (2023). Effectiveness of public health digital surveillance systems for infectious disease prevention and control at mass gatherings: systematic review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 25, e44649.
- Mbunge, E., Muchemwa, B., & Batani, J. (2021). Sensors and healthcare 5.0: transformative shift in virtual care through emerging digital health technologies. *Global Health Journal*, 5(4), 169-177.
- Mello, M. M., & Wang, C. J. (2020). Ethics and governance for digital disease surveillance. *Science*, 368(6494), 951-954.
- Mumtaz, H., Riaz, M. H., Wajid, H., Saqib, M., Zeeshan, M. H., Khan, S. E., Chauhan, Y. R., Sohail, H., & Vohra, L. I. (2023). Current challenges and potential solutions to the use of digital health technologies in evidence generation: a narrative review. *Frontiers in digital health*, 5, 1203945. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdgth.2023.1203945>
- Mustafa, U. K., Kreppel, K. S., Brinkel, J., & Sauli, E. (2023, February). Digital technologies to enhance infectious disease surveillance in Tanzania: a scoping review. In *Healthcare* (Vol. 11, No. 4, p. 470). MDPI.
- Rajvanshi, H., Jain, Y., Kaintura, N., Soni, C., Chandramohan, R., Srinivasan, R., Telasey, V., Bharti, P. K., Jain, D., Surve, M., Saxena, S., Gangamwar, V., Anand, M. S., & Lal, A. A. (2021). A comprehensive mobile application tool for disease surveillance, workforce management and supply chain management for Malaria Elimination Demonstration Project. *Malaria Journal*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-021-03623-3>

- Senbekov, M., Saliev, T., Bukeyeva, Z., Almabayeva, A., Zhanaliyeva, M., Aitenova, N., ... & Fakhradiyev, I. (2020). The recent progress and applications of digital technologies in healthcare: a review. *International journal of telemedicine and applications*, 2020(1), 8830200.
- Shakeri Hossein Abad, Z., Kline, A., Sultana, M., Noaen, M., Nurmambetova, E., Lucini, F., ... & Lee, J. (2021). Digital public health surveillance: a systematic scoping review. *NPJ digital medicine*, 4(1), 41.
- Wang, Q., Su, M., Zhang, M., & Li, R. (2021). Integrating digital technologies and public health to fight Covid-19 pandemic: key technologies, applications, challenges and outlook of digital healthcare. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(11), 6053.
- Yeung, A. W. K., Torkamani, A., Butte, A. J., Glicksberg, B. S., Schuller, B., Rodriguez, B., Ting, D. S. W., Bates, D., Schaden, E., Peng, H., Willschke, H., van der Laak, J., Car, J., Rahimi, K., Celi, L. A., Banach, M., Kletecka-Pulker, M., Kimberger, O., Eils, R., Islam, S. M. S., ... Atanasov, A. G. (2023). The promise of digital healthcare technologies. *Frontiers in public health*, 11, 1196596. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1196596>
- Zhang, L., Guo, W., & Lv, C. (2024). Modern technologies and solutions to enhance surveillance and response systems for emerging zoonotic diseases. *Science in One Health*, 3, 100061.

MD SHAMIDUL KABIR MITAS

1st author & corresponding author

Email: mitasshamidul@gmail.com

Intern Doctor, The Fifth affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University, China

SIRAJUM MUNIRA

2nd author

Email: sirajummunira2022@gmail.com

Intern Doctor, The Second affiliated hospital of Zhengzhou University, China

TAHSIN HOSSAIN LISUN

3rd author

Email:tahsinlisan420@gmail.com

Intern Doctor, The 2nd Affiliated Hospital Of Guangzhou Medical University